

Template - Processing analysis

Template to process all surfaces acquired with the LSM with the 50x/0.75 and 50x/0.95 objectives.

Processing

Identity card			
Name:	Kremasti4_LSM_50x_type1_e_Topo		
Created on:	4/13/2021 4:06:16 PM		
Studiabile type:	Surface		
Axis:	X		
Length:	255.5	µm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Y		
Length:	255.5	µm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	34.77	µm	
Size:	65532	digits	
Spacing:	0.5306	nm	
NM-points ratio:	0.000 % (0 Pts)		

Identity card			
Name:	Kremasti4_LSM_50x_t...filtered (As 2.500 μm)		
File path:	D:\...\Kremasti4_LSM_50x_type1_e_Topo.sur		
Created on:	4/13/2021 4:06:16 PM		
Studiabile type:	Surface		
Axis:	X		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Offset:	0.000	μm	
Axis:	Y		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Offset:	-255.5	μm	
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	6.584	μm	
Min:	-4.113	μm	
Max:	2.471	μm	
Size:	124086	digits	
Spacing:	0.05306	nm	
NM-points ratio:	21.70 % (1952784 Pts)		

Identity card			
Name:	Kremasti4_LSM_50x_ty...in non-measured points		
Created on:	4/13/2021 4:06:16 PM		
Studiable type:	Surface		
Axis:	X		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Y		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	6.584	μm	
Size:	124086	digits	
Spacing:	0.05306	nm	
NM-points ratio:	0.000 % (0 Pts)		

Analyses

8. ISO 25178-2 parameters on surface #7

ISO 25178 - Primary surface			
<i>F: [Workflow] Form removed (LS-poly 3)</i>			
<i>S-filter (λs): [Workflow] S-filtered (λs 2.500 μm)</i>			
Height parameters			
Sq	0.7351	μm	
Ssk	-1.103		
Sku	8.744		
Sp	2.398	μm	
Sv	4.186	μm	
Sz	6.584	μm	
Sa	0.4949	μm	
Functional parameters			
Smr	3.068	%	
Smc	0.7945	μm	
Sxp	1.671	μm	
Spatial parameters			
Sal	22.80	μm	
Str	0.3737		
Std	39.25	°	
Hybrid parameters			
Sdq	0.2544		
Sdr	2.796	%	
Functional parameters (Volume)			
Vm	0.04624	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vv	0.8407	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vmp	0.04624	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vmc	0.4765	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vvc	0.7302	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vvv	0.1105	μm ³ /μm ²	

Analyses:	
ISO 25178	8.
Furrow	9.
Texture direction	10.
Texture isotropy	11.
SSFA	12.

9. Furrow analysis on surface #7

All furrows are shown.

Parameters	Value	Unit
Maximum depth of furrows	4.072	µm
Mean depth of furrows	0.4982	µm
Mean density of furrows	4977	cm/cm2

10. Texture direction on surface #7

Parameters	Value	Unit
First direction	89.99	°
Second direction	135.0	°
Third direction	44.99	°

11. Texture isotropy on surface #7

Parameters	Value	Unit
Texture isotropy	36.19	%

12. SSFA on surface #7

